

Islamic Theology 'Ilm-l-Kalām and Response of Alfas And Ma'lami (Mutakalimun) to Digital Economy Inhibiting Coherence

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Abstract

Theology, 'Ilm-l-Kalām is a discipline, at all levels, that encompasses everyone in one way or the other. Some scholars specialized in theology without wherewithal for it. They are found in every ethnic group, in Yoruba, Hausa and others. The theologians in Yoruba are called Alfas and Ma'alami in Hausa. This work examines Islamic theology among the Yoruba and Hausa communities. It identifies who are Yoruba and Hausa theologians (Mutakalimun)? What are the responsibilities of the theologians? Digital economy is examined and what is the nexus between Islamic theology and digital economy? What are the available digital platforms? Data are garnered through qualitative method and content analysis is considered for the results. It discovered various attacks between theologians within ethnic group. There are misrepresentations and factors inhibiting coherence among them. The paper concludes that digital economy is not used by Islamic theologians from Yoruba and Hausa ethnic groups as expected. It therefore recommends that Alfas and Ma'alami should stop attacking personalities and confront digitalization of economy and propagation of Islam for the development of the Nation.

Keywords: Islamic Theology, 'Ilm-L-Kalām, Mutakalimun, Digital Economy

Introduction

In every society be it inside or outside Nigeria, there is always a group identified to be theologian. The theologian is a name attributed with everyone speaking, acting, arguing and dialoguing in connection with God. A theologian may come from any practicing religions. For instance, In Nigeria, there are religions including Abrahmic beliefs, namely: Judaism, Christianity and Islam in that order. There are ways of discharging the roles and through the practice they are known as theologians. Anything shorts of the expected of them seems to be contrary or ridiculous. The contemporary time is advanced with technology, which is expected that theologians should equally key in. No doubt, economy in view of COVID-19 pandemic which was experienced globally strengthened economic shift from been physical to internet and subsequently to digital. This paper examines theology and a theologian from Yoruba and Hausa ethnic groups. What are their responsibilities? It examines responsibilities of theologian, and nexus between theology and digital economy from Islamicology. Available digital platforms are identified as used in contemporary time. What are the inhibiting factors affecting coherency of theologians?

The questions are answered through qualitative approach using content and observation analyses with a view to providing definition of theology, identifying theologians, bridging relationship of theology and digital economy and extrapolating possible benefits that could be derived economically and religiously. Theologians from the Yoruba and Hausa ethnic groups are chosen as case of study. Yoruba and Hausa could be found in any part of the world, points of reference of this work are western and northern parts of Nigeria. Specifically, in Yorubaland: Oyo, Ogun, Osun and Ilorin-Kwara; Hausa speaking but different ethnics like Sokoto, Maiduguri, Kano, Katsina; and Central Nigeria- Kaduna, Niger, Plateau, Kogi States. This paper identifies kinds of theology, areas of specialization and practice. From the available data, the paper has contributed to knowledge in that series

of attacks between the theologians does not do any good to Islamization of knowledge. The paper concludes and recommends appropriately. The paper begins by providing conceptual definitions and clarification.

Conceptual Clarification

Theology

Examining the concept of theology from Islamic teaching, it explicates that every discussion that connected with Allah is believed to be *Dini* (religion). Theology in a wider sense is a religiously defined method of communicating fundamental issues, refuting claims that are not having evidence to prove beyond any doubt. Scholars have exhaustively discussed what theology ought to mean from various religions, for the purpose of this paper and from Islamicology, theology is the experience of teaching and learning about oneness of Allah, which is called *Illahiyyah*, monotheism. Strong belief in existence of Allah in every existing place in cosmos is the concept of theology. Theology in Islam developed in stages with changes as society grows. From Islamic perspective, scholars have explained series of names through which theology developed.¹ It was, in the beginning, the only responsibility of Prophet Muhammad *Salallahu 'Alayhi was Salam* (SAW), meaning may the peace and blessing of Allah be on him, to present and explain the dos and don'ts in Islam. His death in 632 A.D.² gave opportunity to his companions the responsibility of expressing their understanding about Islam from the prophet to the followers. Six stages of development of theology were identified in Shittu.³ He narrated them with a view to identifying what theology and inherent nature that influencing the cosmos in contemporary societies.

Islamicology

Islamicology is the custodian of theology; it is a new structure or name recently developed in 21st century.⁴ It was formed from two words: Islamic and ology, it becomes a compound noun, which means the study of all aspects of life in connection with Islam. It could be described as a systematic way of Islamizing knowledge and exploring position of Islam in all situations of life. Therefore, Islamicology is referred to teaching and learning all subjects not only in humanity, it includes sciences, businesses and vocations. Experts in Islamicology are directly involved in theology. Two similar terms are in use for the application of theology, that is, *'Ilm-l-Kalām*.⁵

'Ilm-l-Kalām

'Ilm-l-Kalām is an Arabic term coined from two words: *'Ilm* and *Kalām*. First word means knowledge, science, education; while the second refers to word, explanation, speech, discussion and it could mean debate, dialogue *et cetera*. Technically, the word *'Ilm-l-Kalām* means theology because the word *Kalām* emerged from the discussion of Holy Qur'an. In contemporary time, *'Ilm-l-Kalām* has been expanded and presented academically to have covered strata of lives.⁶ Furthermore *'Ilm-l-Kalām* has veritable tools which are applied to effectively deliver message that connects teaching and learning in every gathering and society. This practice does not remove going to internet searching for knowledge and sharing it in digital form. Next to examine is the term digital in contemporary world.

Digital

Digital is a new term taking over from internet. An application that concerns and uses of digit numbers and connects with a computer for an effective communication between two persons or groups. Again, the idea of digital, in practical sense, is incomplete without active internet power, that is, 'data' which gives energy to the internet connectivity and allows digital application to be effective. In other words, digital is any activity passing through computer application; hence digital theology is recently dominating societies.

Digital Theology

Digital theology is a new multidisciplinary field of study. It is an online co-designed project from which learning and teaching are possible. It passes religious messages across many fields to a multicultural and

multidisciplinary group of students. Students hereby refer to audience, which does not limit to a particular set of people or ethnic group or country. Digital theology is an online based with the influence of scientific cultural variety, co-design, designed science research, Scrum, Discord, Trello, GitHub and WordPress. Nevertheless, in all digital designed system, in communication, audio and video are germane.⁷

Digital Economy and Developments

Digital economy refers to all economic activities emanating from an individual or a group connecting individuals, groups on businesses, devices, using data and operations through digital technology. Of course, it differs from any other forms simply it relies on digital technology, online transactions and its transformative effect on traditional industries. The application is very wide that digitalizing or building upon internet makes such an innovation internet related development. It enhances power of economy and areas of coverage within a shortest time and profitable.

Economists and business leaders assert that the digital economy is more advanced and complex than the internet economy, which has just been discovered in 20th century. The COVID-19 pandemic gave concentration and growth to online shopping, telemedicine and digital entertainment during lockdowns and social distancing protocol against COVID-19 pandemic.⁸ Therefore, with emerging technologies and innovations, digital economy and digital theology are shaping their history and trajectory. Several developments have taken place on the digital economy significantly and are noted as follows:

1. Inception of digital trade and e-commerce introduced Amazon, Alibaba and eBay as first generated and transformed buying and selling to online, which reshaped retail and created new technologies and business models for wider societies using networking like Facebook, twitter, Instagram and LinkedIn which changed how people communicate, connect and promote their products. This has influenced the practice of theology, such that learning, reading and memorizing Qur'an and giving lectures through dialect digitally are impressive.
2. A change of attitude to economy view was evolved, especially during global pandemic of COVID-19, which encouraged using applications, like Zoom, slack, Meet and Microsoft Teams to promote online collaboration and communication. Indeed! Congregation on daily and Friday prayers were not physically possible and Juma'at sermons did not lost because of the digital applications.
3. Whole and retailers reach and serve their customers quicker through multiple internet and digital sources named it online sales and mobile apps. This lets them identify buyers, whether they are shopping via the internet or in person. Artificial Intelligent (AI) and automation have significantly shaped the digital economy. It contributed to emergency of digital *Madrasa* school, payment of the school fees and sales of useful materials for Arabic and Islamic education.
4. Mode of Digital payments and crypto-currencies systems like, PayPal, Venmo, Palmpay, and mobile wallets have changed psych and practice of how people conduct financial transactions. These modes and equally lawful to transact under the theology.
5. The entertainment industry has undergone significant changes due to the rise of streaming services such as Netflix, Spotify, Opay and YouTube. Streaming services towards making theological discussion possible and questions can be asked as well as asweres.
6. Telemedicine. The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the spread of telemedicine and made remote medical care possible through digital platforms. Today, telehealth is a crucial component in providing healthcare. Teletheology has been ongoing through all available spheres including televisions.
7. Sharing economy. The sharing economy has transformed how people share resources such as cars, lodging and services. Sharing of ideas in theology and group discussion on theology has been an interesting digital development.
8. Digitalized Theology is a most recent form of practice among theologians especially in Yorubaland and Hausaland. Both young and old have switched to the use of digital mode of theology; it brings about wider

coverage, understanding and enhancement of knowledge. Of course, it is not without challenge such as misuse of the privilege, egocentrism in knowledge, enmity and propagation of *Jalabite* digital economy.⁹

The Theologians among the Yoruba and the Hausa

Theologians among Yoruba are called *Alfas* (pl), *Alfa* (sngl.); In Hausa, *Ma'alami* (pl), *Ma'alam* (sngl.) is a well-informed person educationally, socially, economically and more importantly theologically. They speak their native dialect and concurrently Arabic language during their practice or teaching. It may interest that some scholars passed through institutions of learning, they are versatile technologically and versed in Arabic language than others, yet they are not into practice of theology.

Schools where Islamicologists are trained are in stages: *Tahdir* (Nursery), *Ibtidahiyyah* (Primary), *Hidadiyyah* (Secondary) and *Thanawiyah* or *Thaoji* (Tertiary) levels. Scholars like Fafunwa researched into the classes, through which *Alfa* obtained knowledge of theology. Most scholars in universities with departments of Arabic and Islamic studies (Islamicology),¹⁰ passed through the training. Similarly, in Hausaland, theologians passed through *Karatu Sore* or *Sangaya* (Local School). Everyone in Islamic and Arabic studies passed through these schools. Some of them memorized Qur'an with modern technology. Memorization of Qur'an is one of the common traditional knowledge parents give to their wards. Theologians have classifications: practicing and nominal theologians. The practicing theologians are those preaching through all means including their attitudes and every other available information and technological devices. They are highly esteemed in the society. They teach in their private and unstructured classes while some do impart knowledge in public and structured private schools. Some of the nominal theologians are knowledgeable of both Arabic and Islamic, they teach mostly in tertiary institutions but they lack some attributes, which shall be analysed in later paragraph.

Attributes of Theologians

The characteristics of theologians include but not limited to the following:

1. Everyone who is knowledgeable of Arabic and Islamic teachings, no matter how little is called *Alfa* and *Ma'alam* in Yorubaland and Hausaland respectively. Some of the *Alfas* in Yorubaland are poetic and musically toned especially when they converse or communicate with their audience. Some of them are found in both private and public institutions, and at all level educational set up. Some of them are well informed of western education with which they interact with all class of people at any forum. The *Ma'alami* in Hausaland are not poetical but rendition of Qur'an recitation is logical and melodic.
2. Some *Alfas* are engaging in helping seekers of help through prayers and other means of assistance. The practice of this engagement is called *Jalabi*.¹¹ Most of them pretend to be future tellers and healers. They are not skilful in any vocational works except sitting at home and be consulting. Same is found among the Hausa theologians.
3. Some *Alfas* and *Ma'alami* are well informed and engaged with public offices for teaching in tertiary institutions, yet they are consulting and prescribing spiritually and traditionally concocting substance.
4. Some *Alfas* and *Ma'alamis* are leading Muslim organisations and they drive clients from members especially women wing of the society. They market themselves through any available communication means and praise whatsoever they had at a time done and coincidental with the divine plan.
5. Some of them are rich but many of them are moderately living because of their limited sources of income. They like wearing big designed dress with turban and some are found in luxurious car and mansion.
6. *Alfa* and *Ma'alam* impart knowledge as designed by their role. Many theologians demonstrate their interest in teaching and preaching and they do not follow any rich personalities or leaders of communities or politicians. They are self-contented with what they are provided with naturally or divinely.
7. Yoruba and Hausa theologians include *Imams* (Leaders of Muslim Communities). They lead congregational prayers, officiate naming, house warming, leading pilgrims, lead in ceremonial prayers and conduct *Tafsir*

Quranic (exegetical teaching) during fasting in the month of Ramadan. Of course, they are consulting for various issues, especially in religion.

8. *Alfa* and *Ma'alam* are in the habit of propagating Islam through their knowledge by teaching Arabic and Islamic studies. They go out for preaching accompanied with their students, in the recent past; they visit village's heads for permission and invitation to listen to their narration from the Qur'an and Hadith. They had used local pot-light and pumping glass-light, which is generated from kerosene. They are otherwise called itinerant scholars. Still, in Hausaland, among Izalatul Bid'a wa Iqaamatus Sunnah (JIBWIS), they go out of their areas to preach and/or conduct *Tafsir* lessons. The *Alfas* and *Ma'alami* are versed in the knowledge of Qur'an, exegetic of Qur'an, Hadith, *Fiqh*, *Usulud-Din* and the rest.
9. They are expected to be conscious of Allah privately and in the public especially when dealing with people on human related matters.
10. They are ambassadors of *Rasulu al-Karim* (Glorious Prophet), ambassador of Islam and its culture. In practice, appearance and in speech, the *Alfas* and *Ma'alami* ought to show modality of Islam.
11. Truthfulness and justice are twined moral disciplines that are required from every Muslims, especially from the *Ma'alami* and *Alfas*. At any stage or time in life, when the truth cannot be found elsewhere, it should always be at the disposal of *Ma'alami* and *Alfas*.
12. They are privileged to serve society in local, state and national government. They are privileged to acquire properties and positions but it must be lawful and through legitimate means. They are privileged to be actively involved in politics but not in dirty form of politics where lies and envy are watch-word.

Digital Theology and available Platforms

In the above, the term is conceptualized. Here, the paper examined what digital theology and theologians meant. Digital theology refers to the use of digital means to propagate religions in which Islam is part of. The study of theology is increasingly interested in the virtual spaces in very recent time just between the end of twenty and twenty-first centuries. Practice of theology online demonstrates the online transposition of theology and the use of the internet by theological association or groups based on physical spaces. Theology online includes all the practices and narratives of Islam that exist exclusively online. The proliferation and growth of digital based practices influenced creation of various webs pages and platforms, which made the distinction increasingly blurred. Teaching of Islamicology through every available platform online and through technology is however tagged 'digital theology'. It is not necessary that the discussion must be on monotheistic nature, it includes other issues of religiously concerned. Practice of theology digitally presents the message to global space and large communities of different religious, social, cultural and ethnic background.

There are different platforms that would make theologians practice effectively. The available platforms on social media transposition practice of theology. Among others are

1. Facebook the largest social networking site. A large population of the world uses Facebook. Business people (mostly small businesses) are into Facebook platform, because it actively promotes their business. It is easy to get started on Facebook because almost all content formats work with ease.
2. YouTube is a video-sharing platform where users watch a billion hours of videos daily. Besides being the second largest social media site, YouTube is often called the second largest search engine after Google, its parent company. So if you use video to promote your business, then you definitely need to add YouTube to your marketing strategy.
3. WhatsApp is a messaging application to family members and friends. Gradually, people started communicating with businesses via WhatsApp. WhatsApp's business platform allows businesses to provide customer support and share updates with customers about their purchases.
4. Instagram is a visual social networking platform. Instagram is the place for showcasing products or services with photos or videos. On the app, you can share a wide range of content, such as photos, videos,

stories, and events. As a brand, you can create an Instagram business profile, which provides rich analytics of profile and posts other events.

5. WeChat was released in 2011 by Tencent, one of China's biggest tech companies. Like WhatsApp and Messenger, WeChat was originally a messaging app, but it's evolved into an all-in-one platform. Besides messaging and calling, users can shop online, pay bills, buy groceries, transfer money, make reservations, book taxis, and more. WeChat is the most popular social media platform in China and other parts of Asia.
6. TikTok is a short-form video-sharing app. It was launched in 2017. It is effective because of its fastness and recently overtook Google as the most visited internet site. TikTok allows users to create and share videos between 15 and 60 seconds long.¹²

There are others that this paper may not accommodate. Theologians are free to use any of the above platforms depending on which of them they are familiar with. Each of them is equally simple to learn and work with.

Nexus between Islamic Theology and Digital Economy

Nexus between Islamic Theology and digital economy is the relationship that exists in digitalization and economy, ditto the interaction of Islamic theology through digital space. Everything that is possible in economy online has no barrier to theological digitalization. The theologians are engaging in some economic activities, it is therefore expected that the available platforms are as useful for them as others are making economic benefit from them.

The theologians have ample opportunity to explore maximally utilization of digital form of communication economically and theologically but the reverse is always be the case. The platforms are currently employed to abuse one another, for instance:

1. Writing of lampoon: Some *Alfas* and *Ma'alami* on various platforms especially Facebook write with a view to attacking others. Institutionally, one is feeling more superior to the others, especially between the students from Markaz, Agege and Adabiyyah from Ilorin. Incidentally the proprietors of these institutions were from Ilorin and contemporary. Whereas the act is outside the role of theologians and all the students are claiming to be theologians.
2. They consider platforms to be global opportunity where they could display their intelligent. It is a good practice but this is done in several forms that debase integrity of others and against the ethic of both the theology and utilization of digital platforms.
3. Theology accommodates argumentation, discussion and disputation and the rest that could enhance knowledge. The *Alfas* and *Ma'alami* pick offence in one another. They engage in criticizing one another, to the extent of addressing themselves to be lunatics. This act alone has caused various divisions among them. The act is attributed to the two mentioned in one above and strongly connected with the *Izalatul Bid'ah wa Iqamatul Sunnah* and the *Fityanu* sects. Both are not only castigating one another but also condemning themselves to *Kafir* unbeliever. This is very dangerous to both sides.
4. Yoruba without the act of respect is bankrupt of decency.¹³ The younger *Alfas* and *Ma'alami* that are expected to learn from the experiences of the older started condemning knowledge of elders and placing them wrongly to Islamic ethics.
5. Some *Alfas* have turned the platforms to music concert grounds where they display their dramatic and musical experiences to the world by lambasting their colleagues without necessary see any of them. This act is not the same with Hausa theologians.
6. Some *Alfas* in Yoruba speaking areas have been engaging in digitalization of birthday program. This has just been noticed recently but Hausa theologians are exempted. This simple act derails the role of a theologian. Older *Alfas* are addressed as Shaykh because of their age and knowledge especially their contribution to the pool of knowledge at their places of residence and outside. This title is common to both ethnic groups

7. Some *Alfas* and *Ma'alami* among Yoruba and Hausa of contemporary period are engaging in bitter arguments even against traditionally religious adherents in a manner that could not bring understanding of Islam. It rather enhances enmity. The dispositions become source of separations among the *Alfas* and create unhealthy relationship even among the *Ma'alami* of various sects and organizations in Hausaland.

Expected Responsibilities of Digital Theologians

Digital theologians are expected to ensure adequate knowledge is imparted in the society and transposition it to digital platform. Knowledge of *Iman*, the belief in Oneness of Allah is the major message to the world. It is required that principles of Islam which are the foundation should be priority of *Alfas* on the internet for global consumption. In complacent, articles of faith required adequate theological explanation to avoid some misconception about the teaching of Islam. Contemporary emerging issues can be examined from theological perspectives. This is one of the major concerns of Islamic theology. Islamization of knowledge is a major role of theologians such that Muslim world benefits from existing ocean of knowledge and exhibition of *jihad* (religious exertion).

There is nothing wrong in ensuring the Muslims through the digital theological process extend the knowledge of prophetic medicine. This shall bring such understanding of prophetic way of treating illness and diseases. Contemporary *Alfas* and *Ma'alami* have obligation of ensuring understanding of Islamicology. Historical connection to conflicts and ways of resolving them is expected to be digitalized for the world to benefit from. The practice of Prophet Muhammad (SAW) *Sunnah* (way and manner) that he had settled several conflicts in both Makkah and Madinah among the residents as well as between clans (Aws and Khasraj).¹⁴

Islamic form of business, banking, finance, insurance, buying and selling through digitalization and theological expressions, *Alfas* and *Ma'alami* are to engage people for the progress of Muslim globally. There are rules guiding every aspect of economy mentioned, relevance of Islamic guides to their operation are to be presented to the world. This could bring comparison or evaluation along with others to establish most profitable and lawful in the sight of Allah.

Misrepresentation of Theologians

On the platforms, especially the Facebook, theologians represent neither Islam nor teaching the theology. They lampoon one another, attack whom they classified to be their enemies and who they suspect is accusing their authority. This is rampant and alarming with which it is affecting nature of theology and raising a question of what and who do they represent on the net? There are respected Arabic and Islamic institutions in Yoruba speaking areas. Markaz Arabic Institute, Mahdul Arabi Ibadan, Mahd Ashar Al-Adabi Ilorin and many which they have produced erudite scholars of Islamicology and Western education. Many of them have reached the pinnacle of their carrier and retired from their service. It appears in contemporary time that the younger colleagues and few among the respected *Alfas* and *Ma'alami* take to their facebook, You Tube to address audience in a manner that disrespect theology and has nothing to do with it. They are knowledgeable but there is no application method for them to effectively impart knowledge through the platforms. Their intent seems to be different from what digital theology should be and not realized implication of what they do on the global space.

Inhibiting Factors of Coherence

There are some factors affecting them which obvious affecting inability to unite and carry out role of theologians. Some of them are:

1. Socialization has been prioritized in the young theologians, such that they want to be seen and known for their presentation on the global space
2. Materialism is already taken over the interest of theology in their heart and therefore they tend to explore all sources that could bring what they desire.

3. Demonstration of their talent among their colleagues and ovation they often receive from congregation affects their interest and cohesion. They struggle for the best among themselves and seniority. They exhibit their pride in such a way that negatively affects cohesion.
4. Finally, everyone is targeting money and other materials which have been the bane of lack of trust, development and unity among the theologians. It has indeed enmeshed the theologians to which they hardly disentangle themselves. One wonders if they are socialists, film actors or musicians!

Conclusion

In Yoruba and Hausa speaking societies, small and big Arabic and Islamic schools are uncountable established for the purpose of teaching and learning Islam and its culture. From them through other conventional institutions, professors are produced. They have acquired ample knowledge with a lot of experiences from their global exposure and they did transposition it on digital space. Unfortunately the language through which it was done is official language (English) and not cultural mother language. It has been established that some *Alfas* and *Ma'alami* on digital space are well vocal in official language but they engage in accusation of one another. They are expected to give better explanation and not comparing understanding of knowledge, ridiculing and insulting one another. Beyond digital theology, in order to sustain survival through economy, there are many possible economic engagements and advertisements that theologians can create and benefit from. This is the area that theologians have not explored positively.

Recommendations

1. The *Alfas* and *Ma'alami* are in the best position to bring knowledge of Islam to digital space at their schools. Therefore they are encouraged to strengthen their effort through digitalization.
2. They should collaborate with others to ensure adequate and wide spread of theological message on the digital space. Mode of operating acceptable economic engagement in Islam should be enhanced for wider coverage.
3. Both of them should stop writing lampoon and exhibit assaults on one another. Knowledge is an ocean which no one is capable of navigating through. They should see digital theology as a source of learning and teaching global class of students.
4. Older contemporary *Alfas* and *Ma'alami* should accommodate the younger ones to empower them on digitalization of theology and *modus operandi* in public space. The younger theologians should respect older and more knowledgeable so that they can acquire adequate knowledge to present on digital space.
5. Imams in all Muslim organisations are theologians, their Friday *Khutuba* (talk) should be transferred to digital space for global consumption and practice. Not only Friday talk, seminar and workshop lectures should equally be made available on digital space.
6. Digitalization of theology is highly economical and has wider coverage than physical presentation. A button would make a heavy message sent to global village in a second with smallest required data of fifty (N50) only. Some groups are coming up in this direction.

Endnotes

¹Scholars like Abduh, Muhammad. *Risala at-Tawhid*. (Cairo: Dar al-Manar, 1366AH). Others include al-Ahwani Ahmad Fuad; Shittu Huud, etc.

²Nadwi, Ali S. Abu Hasan, *Muhammad Rasulullah*. (India: Academy of Islamic Research and Publication, 1979),184-194.

³Shittu, Huud. *‘Ilm-l-Kalām: A Niche for Islamicology and other Disciplines and a requisite for Dons, Administrators and Bureaucrats in Contemporary Nigeria*. (Jos: UP, Tuesday Feb 21 2023) 56.

⁴Huud Shittu “Evolution and development of the Islamicology in Jos-Plateau”. *Liwuram: Journal of the Humanity*, Vol. 18. (Maiduguri, 2017), 335-347.

⁵Abdulrazaq O. Kilani. *Islamology. Fouth Edition*. (Ado-Ekiti: Horizon Print & Publishing, 2019), 23.

⁶Shittu, Huud. *‘Ilm-l-Kalām: A Niche for Islamicology and other Disciplines and a requisite for Dons, Administrators and Bureaucrats in Contemporary Nigeria*. (Jos: UP, Tuesday Feb 21 2023).

⁷Digital economy was first coined in 1995. Tapscott, Don. *The Digital Economy: Promise and Peril in the Age of Networked Intelligence*.

⁸The world experienced fear and loss of several economic opportunities for e whole year. Life for people was very tense but rate of crimes were reduced.

⁹*Jalabite* is englishized from the Arabic word *Jalab*, which mean to draw linguistically. Technically it is a nature of work that attracts clients for spiritual requests or consultation.

¹⁰Huud Shittu. "Islamicology: Educational Concept," *International Journal of Continuing Education*. (Jos: Center for Continuing Education, July 2013), 54-72.

¹¹<https://buffer.com/library/social-media-sites/11Shittu>, Huud. "Islam and 'Respect' in Yoruba Cultural Cosmos," *Journal of University scholars in Religions. Issue No. 4*. (Osogbo: Jemilah, 2014), 599-613.

¹²Nadwi, Ali S. Abu Hasan, 184-194.